

ISic3505

I.Sicily inscription 3505

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

stone

Object

pavement

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

pavement of bouleuterion, Segesta; excavation SAS 3 (except fr.a found much earlier)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140596

1. Ἀσκλαπὸς [— —]

2. ΕΠΠ [— — —]

3.

Edition: PHI336567

1. Ἄσκληπος Διοδώρου Ταυρέας

2. ἐπιστάτας,

3. Βίβακος Τιττέλου Ποσθαῖος

4. ἀρχιτεκτόνησε.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492729

EDCS 39102270

PHI 140596

PHI 336567

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0292 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 50.1020

Dubois, Laurent 2008. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile. Tome II.. Geneva. At 88

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliae obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquae tabulae, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At 49 no.323

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5547

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezzenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5193

Nenci, G. 2000. Varia Elyma: novità epigrafiche, numismatiche, toponomastiche e culturali dall'area elima.

Terze Giornate Internazionale di studi sull'area elima. Atti. Pisa. pp. 809-821. At 810-811 tav.156

De Vido, S. 2003. Genealogie Segestane.

Quarte

Giornate Internazionali di Studi sull'area elima, Erice, 1-4 dicembre 2000. Pisa. pp. 367-402. At 400 no.13

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. Inscriptiones Segestanae. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Segesta. Pisa. At G14

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3505. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388684>